

Śiva-Cult in Ancient India and Present Religious Trend of Śiva-worship in Assam: A Continuing Tradition

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Śaivism is the most popular and religious sects of Hinduism where Lord Śiva is regarded as the Supreme Self or the Highest Reality. There are many sub-sects within Śaivism. Of the different sects that survived the vicissitudes of time there are mainly five well-known systems of Śaivism. These are: Pâúupata Śaivism, Śaiva-Siddhânta, Úrîka Gmha's philosophy, Vîra-Śaivism and Pratyabhijñâ Śaivism.

The worship of the *liEga* is the essence of Śiva theology through the centuries. The worship of the *liEga* is prevalent in India from pre-epic period. It is said in the PurâGas that only Lord Śiva can be worshipped both in an image and phallic form but the other deities worshipped only in an image form. There are so many rites and rituals are observed in ancient India such as *Pâúupatavrata*, *Úivarâtrivrata*, *Kcîradhârâvrata* etc.

From pre-historic period to contemporary period, Śaivism as a religious system seems to be the most practiced faith in Assam. The inhabitants of Assam preserve their own systems of Śaiva practice, which is original and distinct in character. So many rites and rituals of Śiva-worship are observed here. Different forms of Lord Śiva are found to be worshipped among different communities of Assam. Mention may be made of *Bâthou*, *Lâlung*, *Bûrhâ-Gosâin* etc. But it is observed that among these different forms of Śiva rituals there is a continuity of tradition from very remote past.

In the present paper an attempt will be made to showcase this continuous tradition of Śiva rituals in the context of present day Assam.